

The Importance of Motivation in Classroom Learning

Nurmetova Mohimjon Ortiq Qizi

Teacher, Uzbekistan State University of World Languages

nurmetova.mohimjon@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The focus of this article is on the relationship between students' needs, interests, goals and expectations towards learning EFL and teachers' roles as motivators. There is an extensive body of literature addressing the issue of students' motivation in the classroom. This can include many different variables, among which are motivation (intrinsic and extrinsic), lack of orientation, self-confidence, interest and practical goals/objectives. However, lack of orientation, self-confidence, interest and practical objectives are all intertwined with the broader issue, which is motivation, either intrinsic or extrinsic, and therefore they can be grouped and referred to simultaneously as aspects of motivation.

Keywords: *self-acquisition, education, cognitive processes, motivation.*

The formation of motivation for learning activities can be called one of the central problems of the modern education. Its relevance is due to the updating of the content of education, the setting of tasks for the formation of cognitive processes in students, methods of self-acquisition of knowledge and an active life position.

As you know, motivating factors are crucial for achieving positive learning outcomes, i.e. external and internal driving forces. Many experts talk about the need to purposefully form students' motivation for learning activities, noting that the formation of motives for learning activities is much more difficult than the formation of actions and operations [8].

An analysis of studies on the problem of motivation for learning activities reveals a wide variety of motives that affect the effectiveness of learning. This is due, among other things, to age-related features. However, the most common

reason for poor assimilation of knowledge and ineffective learning activities is low motivation for learning, the lack of meaning of learning. The most problematic in this regard is adolescence.

Many psychologists have studied motivation, therefore, in modern psychological science, a wide variety of its interpretations are presented. So, A.K. Markova under the motives of teaching, learning activity understands the focus of the student on different aspects of learning activity. Accordingly, motives can be cognitive, if they are related to the content of the teaching, and social, if they are related to the communication of students with each other and with teachers. The most complete is the understanding of motivation in the activity theory of learning (P.Ya. Galperin, D.B. Elkonin, V.V. Davydov, N.F. Talyzina, etc.). The motive can be external or internal, depending on the attitude of a person to the process of obtaining knowledge [5].

If the motivation for learning is external, this does not mean that it is bad, it has its own advantages and disadvantages. It is known that prestigious and competitive motivations are widespread in the educational environment and often lead to good academic results. Competitive motivation is a typical phenomenon in high school when children try to keep up with each other. Prestigious motivation works for high school students who are trying to assert themselves by demonstrating their knowledge in a particular area. These comments inevitably lead one to think that these students have low intrinsic or extrinsic motivation to learn English. Whatever the case may be, a basic truth is that students, who are not motivated to learn, do not learn. Unfortunately, there is no magic bullet for motivating students. Many factors influence students' motivation to learn: interest in the subject matter, perception of its usefulness, general desire to attain, self-confidence and self-esteem, as well as patience and persistence (Bligh, 1971, Sass, 1989 as cited in Davis 1999). It is also important to take into account that not all

students are motivated by the same values, needs, desires, or wants. Some students may be motivated by the approval of others (peer acceptance), some by defeating challenges, while others seem naturally excited about learning. However, many students need or expect their teachers to inspire, challenge, and stimulate them. Ericksen stated that, "effective learning in the classroom depends on the teacher's ability... to maintain the interest that brought students to the course in the first place" (1978 p. 3). Whatever level of motivation students bring to the classroom will be converted, for better or worse, by what happens in that classroom. Students' motivation to keep learning English after the first year and throughout the following years of secondary school can highly depend on the teacher's ability to maintain the initial interest that brought the students into the English classroom. In this context, a major importance can be attributed to the teachers' qualifications in the area of English teaching. Teachers need to know and implement teaching techniques and strategies that promote effective learning at the level of the students while at the same time developing interest in the subject matter with materials that are relevant to students' lives and which challenge their knowledge.

Is motivation something innate that is born within us and can be roused and stimulated by reinforcement external to the learning task? Is it something linked to the learning process itself? Or is it a combination of both? Keeping these central questions in mind, I will discuss throughout this paper what the difference is between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, the main theories that support each of the two views and find out how Cape Verdean students learning English for the first time fit in the two categories. I will also refer to the strategies that Cape Verdean teachers have been using addressing each type of motivation and refer to effectiveness or oneffectiveness of those strategies in motivating students to learn English. Experienced teachers understand that it is essential to keep students motivated in order to achieve the best learning results as possible (Weibelzahl &

Kelly, n.d.). Motivation is a widely used variable in many educational and other studies. While it is difficult to define in words, the following simple description captures its essence: Motivation involves the internal processes that give behaviour its energy and direction. Motivation originates from a variety of sources (needs, cognitions and emotions) and these internal processes energize behaviour in multiple ways such as starting, sustaining, intensifying, focusing, and stopping it. (Reeve, 1996, p. 2) Motivation to learn is based on intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, goal orientation, and the student's level of involvement in learning tasks (Woolfolk, 2001 as cited in Merlin, 2003, p. 7). Most motivation theorists assume that motivation is implicated in the performance of all learned responses, that is, a learned behaviour will not happen unless it is Individuals are said to be driven to act for extrinsic reasons when they anticipate some kind of tangible reward, such as recognition, gold stars or, in the case of the students, good grades. These rewards are called extrinsic because they are unrelated to the action. In effect, the activity becomes a means to an end. By contrast, individuals are said to be intrinsically motivated when they engage in activities for their own sake. In this instance, the rewards reside in the actions themselves, making the actions their own reinforcement. In short, in the case of intrinsic motivation, the repetition of an action does not depend as much on some external incentive but on the satisfaction derived from overcoming a personal challenge, learning something new, or discovering things of personal interest. The distinction between the two types of motivation is worth keeping in mind for tworeasons. First, most theories of motivation tend to rely on one or the other or a combination of the two attempting to explain the why of human behaviour. Both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation are essential to a complete understanding of why we do the things we do.

Second, when studying how to influence human behaviour we should recognize that neither an intrinsic nor an extrinsic strategy is better than the other,

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but both have their uses and limitations (Kolesnik, 1978 p.7). Although intrinsic methods might work well with some students, extrinsic techniques might be more productive with others. Moreover, intrinsic and extrinsic strategies might differ widely in their effects. For example, while extrinsic motivation might seem to be more useful in coming up with immediate observable outcomes, intrinsic strategies bring benefits in the long term that might be far more desirable. That in turn will keep students more involved in the tasks at present and prepare them to better deal with the difficulties and obstacles they might face in the future. Studies of intrinsic motivation have related high levels of interest to valuing, engaging in and persisting at a specific task. For instance, when psychologists speak of motivation, they typically refer to the reasons why individuals are stimulated to act. Although student motivation has to do with students' desire to participate in the learning process it also concerns the reasons or goals that underlie their involvement or noninvolvement in academic activities. A student who is intrinsically motivated accepts an activity for its own sake, for the enjoyment it provides, the learning it permits, or the feelings of accomplishment it evokes. An extrinsically motivated student performs in order to obtain some reward or avoid some punishment external to the activity itself, such as grades or teacher approval. The first view is supported by the humanistic theories of motivation which stresses the need for personal growth or development and places a great deal of importance on the concept of "total person" grounded in the premise that people want to fulfill their total potential as human beings, and the cognitive theory of motivation, which explains motivation in terms of a person's continued search for meaning and satisfaction in life(Kolesnik, 1978, p. 8).

On the other hand, behaviourist theory relies much more heavily on incentives (Kolesnik, 1978, p. 76), thus supporting the second view. Incentives are directly related to reinforcement, which is responsible for behaviour modification.

A reinforcer is, in simple terms an event that occurs after behaviour and causes its repetition. One of the key ideas of behaviour modification is that behaviour is fashioned by its consequences. Thus, from the behavioural point of view, the most effective way (and possibly, the only effective way) to arouse and sustain students' interests and to motivate them to engage in a task is to reward their wanted behaviour or to offer them some sort of incentive. One of the most important functions of a teacher is, therefore, to provide suitable reinforcement. However, the line between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation is not always clear. Consequently, there is no dichotomy between interests and incentives in classroom motivation. Teachers are well advised to think of the two, not in either/or terms but as complementing one another. (Avila and Purkey, 1971 as cited in Kolesnik, 1978 p. 180). That is to say that, as teachers, we should not rely only on one type of motivation with regard to the things we do in the classroom towards our students. Sometimes we need to see external reinforcements and other times we have to appeal to students' willingness to learn for his/her own sake by emphasizing the interest on the task itself. Nevertheless, the most important thing we can do is to avoid the overuse of one type of motivation and try to balance the two.

References:

1. Anderman, L. H. & Midgley, C. (1998). Motivation and Middle school Students
2. Deci, E. L. (1992). The Relation of Interest to the Motivation of Behaviour: A
3. Self Determination Theory Perspective. In K. A. Renninger, S. Hidi, & A. Krapp (Eds.), The Role of Interest in Learning and Development (pp. 43-70). Hilldale, NJ: Erlbaum.
4. Huitt, W. (2001). Motivation to learn: An overview. Educational Psychology Interactive. Valdosta, GA: Valdosta State University. Retrieved February 17, 2008
5. Covington, M.V. (2000). Intrinsic Versus Extrinsic Motivation in Schools: A Reconciliation. Berkeley, CA: University of California.

- E. L. & Ryan, R. M. (1985). *Intrinsic Motivation and Self-Determination in Human Behavior*. New York: Plenum Press.
6. Eccles, J. et al (1983). Expectancies, Values and Academic Behaviours. In J.T. Spence (Ed.). *Achievement and Achievement Motivation* (pp. 75-146). San Francisco, CA:W.H.Freeman
 7. Makhamadinovna, U. K. (2023). APPLICATION OF DISTANCE EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION AND DEVELOPING STUDENTS LINGUISTIC COMPETENCE. *British View*, 8(1).
 8. Abbasovna, A. S., & Mahamadinovna, U. K. (2020). Developing Professional Skills Of Students In Foreign Language Education (In Non-Phylological Universities). *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7(03), 2020.